
**D-2.1 Inventory of tools for
systematic risk-
assessment via
questionnaire**
Workpackage 2
Task 2.1

Responsible Partner: APHA

Contributing partners: All partners &
external attendees of D-2.2

GENERAL INFORMATION

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	OTHER: will be accessible publicly through D-2.3

INVENTORY OF TOOLS FOR RISK ASSESSMENT

Inventory

1. Assembly and evaluation of publicly available risk assessment methods and tools.

Through research on Gov.uk, ECDC, EFSA, and scholarly articles, and using that done by the EU FORA fellow Irena Smeu, a list of risk assessment tools and methods were found and evaluated. The list of tools included in the inventory are as follows:

1. The ECDC tool for prioritization of infectious diseases
2. Belgian multidisciplinary evidence based prioritization tool
3. MINTRISK
4. SPARE project
5. HAIRS risk assessment framework
6. Multicriteria based food borne parasite ranking system
7. Simplified generic prioritization tool
8. Prioritisation of companion animal transmissible diseases tool
9. Emerging threat highlight report
10. D2R2
11. Monte Carlo simulation
12. OIE qualitative risk assessment framework
13. OIE quantitative risk assessment framework
14. IDM Risk of incursion tool

1.1. Labelling of Risk Assessment tools

Each Risk assessment method is best suited to particular geographical zones and some may be preferable in different circumstances. The attributes of each tool are summarized below:

1. ECDC tool for prioritizing infectious diseases

- Qualifies the risk of incursion and the social and economic impact that incursion would entail
- Is not constricted to known diseases and is able to rank them based on the user's criteria
- Not designed to be used alone to assess risk, but in supplement to other tools
- The tool uses an excel interface

2. The Belgian multidisciplinary evidence based prioritization tool

- Qualifies the risk of incursion and the social and economic impact that incursion would entail
- Is constricted to 86 known diseases
- Interface is an R document, which is not yet publicly available

3. MINTRISK

- Quantifies the risk of incursion of known vector borne diseases
- European-wide risk tool.
- Considers a wide range of parameters and uses a diverse range of data types to achieve a risk estimate.
- Uses an excel interface

4. SPARE

- Qualifies the risk of incursion to a range of European countries
- Provides a risk output to be used in a formal risk assessment
- Specialises in exotic diseases

- Uses a web-based interface
- 5. HAIRS Risk assessment framework**
 - An adaptive, rapid, qualitative risk assessment framework
 - Can be used for any disease in any situation
 - Relies heavily on expert opinion and relevant literature
 - The success of the risk assessment depends on the wealth of available literature
 - 6. Multicriteria based parasite ranking system**
 - Qualifies the social and economic impact of disease incursion
 - Constricted to known diseases
 - Not location dependent
 - Prioritises risk based on responses to an online questionnaire
 - 7. Simplified generic prioritization tool (France)**
 - Quantifies the risks of known non-exotic diseases (endemic to France)
 - Quantifies their impact on public and animal health
 - Uses an excel interface
 - 8. Prioritisation of companion animal diseases tool**
 - Specific to diseases associated with companion animals
 - Prioritisation largely based on expert opinion
 - Covers impact assessment on agriculture and economy
 - 9. Emerging Threat Highlight Report**
 - Uses and Excel interface
 - Assesses social/economic impact of incurring diseases and other threats
 - 10. D2R2**
 - Prioritises and summarises known exotic and endemic diseases
 - Produces a risk score and describes the impact of diseases post-incursion
 - Built in excel
 - D2R2 method is publicly available though the tool is not
 - 11. Monte Carlo Simulation (bespoke models)**
 - Requires skills in basic statistics and modelling
 - Requires a high detail of data
 - Creates a numeric output that are mathematically dependent on the inputs
 - 12. OIE Qualitative Risk Assessment framework**
 - Highly adaptable template for qualitative risk assessment
 - Is easily constructed and requires little risk assessment experience to implement
 - If well parameterised, can be useful and impactful, but has the potential to lack detail and/or accuracy.
 - 13. OIE Quantitative Risk Assessment framework**
 - Requires skills in basic statistics and modelling
 - Requires a high detail of data
 - Provides a high level of detail
 - 14. IDM Risk of Incursion tool**
 - Only applicable for UK import risk assessments
 - Highly data rich
 - Excel interface
 - Takes commodities as inputs to produce a risk of incursion in to the UK

1.2. Deciding on a Risk Assessment method: creating a decision making tool (D-2.3)

A series of questions were structured to gauge the user's wishlist with regards to a risk assessment. The questions increasingly narrow down to a particular risk assessment type. Aspects such as the user's desire for a 'risk of incursion' tool as opposed to an 'economic/social impact assessment tool' were discerned. Some tools were only suggested if the user was in possession of a required quality of data or had a required skillset.

These questions and their constituent answers were built in a JSON datastructure. Questions functioned as nodes, with answers that would act as the root for the next question. The idea behind this was to

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keep the datastructure simple, and allow questions and answers to be changed or adapted easily if required, without changing the code of the tool itself. The tool is designed to read from the data structure, presenting questions in sequence depending on answers given to previous question.

Delivered as D-2.3 The tool can be accessed from <https://rawcdn.githack.com/RDewar/Decision-support-tool-EJP/11dc62078461ce5f1508cbcd8f1e7c427fa22186/Workingtool1.html>

An offline bundle is available on request if there are access issues email: Rob.Dewar@apha.gov.uk